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ANALYSIS OF FACTORS DESCRIBING AND EXPLAINING THE STANDARD OF LIVING IN ARMENIA USING A VECTOR AUTOREGRESSIVE MODEL¹

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the study is to determine the nature and significance of the influence of the main internal and external economic factors (including revenues and expenditures of the state budget) on indicators characterizing the standard of living. In the current study, an attempt was made to assess the role of various macroeconomic factors, including internal and external economic factors influencing changes in living standards, using a vector autoregressive model. The study used quarterly data of individual indicators for 2008-2024. The growth patterns of indicators describing the standard of living were also touched upon, in particular, they were derived, to what extent the observed changes in the factor are explained by internal and external indicators included in the system. Within the framework of the factors considered, the share of consumer loans in GDP and a relatively lower unemployment and inflation level has the most tangible impact. Inflation and its expectations can also lead to changes in the current reduction in consumption or its dynamics, changing the behavior of households, including reactions to budget revenues and expenditures, GDP per capita, and indicators characterizing the standard of living, in general, are relatively not noticeable. As a result of the study, the order of importance of the role of the observed internal and external factors in changes in indicators characterizing the standard of living was revealed under a decrease in the overall effect over 4 years.

Keywords: standard of living, GDP per capita, poverty level, Gini coefficient, wages, consumption, internal and external factors.

Introduction

The standard of living is a pivotal determinant of population well-being, which includes several socio-economic indicators, including income, employment, education, health, and housing. The standard of living is often characterized by indicators such as gross domestic product (GDP) per capita, unemployment, poverty, income, consumption, and access to basic services. These indicators are influenced by many interrelated factors: The economic development in Armenia has not gone smoothly. The country's economic environment has been shaped by several challenges, including post-Soviet economic restructuring, financial crises, global epidemics, and regional conflicts. This has resulted in fluctuations in living standards, which are

characterized by significant differences between urban and rural areas and various socio-economic groups. Income is a principal factor influencing the standard of living, which directly affects purchasing power and the quality of household consumption. The development of the Armenian economy, which depends on transfers, agriculture, and, more recently, the IT sector, represents a distinctive system of intricate problems and opportunities in this regard. The availability of employment opportunities and the level of remuneration are of paramount importance in determining household income. Inequality in income distribution serves to reinforce socioeconomic inequality, which, in turn, exerts a considerable influence on the volume, quality, and structure of consumption. It is therefore evident that the

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government's fiscal policy plays an important role in the reduction of inequality. Consequently, policymakers and stakeholders must gain a comprehensive understanding of the factors involved to develop effective strategies aimed at improving the quality of life of the population. The objective of this study is to ascertain the nature and significance of the impact of the principal internal and external economic factors (including revenues and expenditures of the state budget) on indicators that characterize the standard of living.

Literature review

Identifying the factors that influence the formation of living standards has always been a focus of attention for various researchers and policymakers. Identifying the causes of inequality and increasing the inclusiveness of policies are the main objectives. The choice of the range and composition of factors considered depends on the characteristics of the country or countries, existing trends and the methods used in the study: Some modern researchers consider it important to assess the impact of economic freedom on living standards. Pelayo Moricel and others, in their study on the impact of economic freedom on living standards and economic growth, try to analyse how economic decisions taken by governments in emerging economies, based on economic freedom, affect economic growth and human development [1]. The analysis is based on panel data for the period 2013-2022, comprising 53 developing countries in Latin America and Asia. The results indicate that there is a statistically insignificant relationship between economic freedom and human development. This research contributes to a more nuanced understanding of the functioning of free market-based policy models and enhances the quality of policy implementation. In economies that rely on external currency flows, it is crucial to assess the influence of foreign exchange reserves and flows on the standard of living and the underlying factors that shape it. In their study, V. Kanishka and V. Lakmal examine the impact of foreign exchange reserves on the standard of living of Sri Lankan citizens [2]. In order to elucidate the underlying causes of the crisis situation in Sri Lanka, a number of economic variables have been identified for further analysis. These include exports, external debt, transfers and foreign exchange reserves. The authors consider gross national income per capita to be a factor that characterises the standard of living. The results demonstrated that exports, external debt and foreign exchange reserves exerted a positive and statistically significant influence on the standard of living of Sri Lankan citizens. Conversely, foreign transfers did not exhibit a notable impact. H. Jingwe and colleagues seek to conceptualise shifts in living standards in developing countries as analogous to carbon dioxide emissions in the context of economic growth [3]. The challenge facing developing countries, defined as low- and middle-income countries with rapid population and GDP growth, is to improve living standards while stabilizing carbon dioxide emissions. The authors quantify the emissions required to achieve a satisfactory standard of living in emerging economies. The findings indicate that, in comparison to other regions, the attainment of a satisfactory quality of life in emerging market countries will result in incremental emissions that do not pose a threat to the global

climate. However, an alarming trend is emerging, with more than half (62 out of 121) of emerging market countries facing significant challenges in achieving the expected growth in emissions.

This is to certify that: In their analysis of the challenges facing humanity in recent years, Kucheryava and A. Karalev highlight the necessity for a more comprehensive approach to ensuring a decent standard of living. They argue that this should encompass not only material needs but also the spiritual dimensions of human existence [4]. An evaluation of the principal characteristics and indicators of living standards in the most developed countries in the world reveals that the countries in the eurozone lead in most parameters. However, the impact of the coronavirus pandemic and the Russian-Ukrainian war has significantly constrained the capacity of governments to maintain these standards. The authors posit that the foundation for sustaining a consistently elevated standard of living in leading countries is the income policy pursued by their governments. This primarily entails maintaining a high level of labour and, consequently, high wages. In their article, N. Gerasimchuk, O. Pashchenko and O. Zharikova examine the structure of income and expenditure of the rural population in Ukraine and its impact on living standards [5]. The authors posit that, despite the favorable trends in wage growth, the remuneration received by those employed in the agricultural sector remains at a markedly low level. Ultimately, it is shaped by a multitude of factors, including inflationary pressures, the broader economic context within the country, government regulations, and other considerations. This is due to the absence of requisite financial resources for consumption. Consequently, rural households engage in the production of foodstuffs to satisfy their personal requirements. The deficit in essential food consumption is offset by an increase in the consumption of oil, other vegetable fats and flour products. An increase in the proportion of expenditure on non-food products is indicative of an improvement in the standard of living experienced by rural households. The low wages of the working-age population, coupled with cultural and household needs, and the lack of developed infrastructure, have a detrimental impact on the standard of living of the rural population, leading to a significant exodus to urban areas. The ongoing conflict between Russia and Ukraine has further exacerbated the situation, resulting in a notable decline in the standard of living of households. The reduction in income and the rise in household expenditure were influenced by several factors, including job loss, a lack of stable income, the necessity for unplanned expenditure and the migration of the population, as well as the threat to life and the resulting fear. In a separate study based on the Thai economy, the authors demonstrate that, despite historically high GDP growth rates, the country experienced a recession following the global pandemic caused by the global crisis and trade tensions [6]. The authors examine the role of sectoral investments, underscoring the preponderant influence of services and industries in which agriculture plays a diminished but nevertheless substantial role. The study analyses a number of key economic indicators, including the level of investment,

government spending, net exports and industrial products, and their impact on GDP. The majority of the analysis is dedicated to an examination of public policy, infrastructure development, trade and investment, as well as social considerations that have an impact on economic performance and living standards. The authors highlight the intricate interrelationship between economic growth and living standards in Thailand. The necessity for continued political reform, investment in infrastructure and the resolution of socio-economic issues is emphasised in order to guarantee sustainable development and enhance living standards.

Additionally, the Armenian researchers addressed the analysis of the factors that determine the standard of living. In their article on the analysis of incomes and expenditures of the population of the Republic of Armenia, R. Ghazaryan and S. Levonyan examine the composition and structure of household incomes and expenditures, as well as their dynamics over the past decade. The indicators were also subjected to analysis at the level of ten decile groups, which serves to indicate the degree of concentration of income among the population. In conclusion, the authors posit that the growth rate of the population's income in Armenia exceeds the growth rate of expenses. In 2018, the lowest decile group experienced a significant increase in income, largely attributable to wage income. The proportion of expenditure on services across all decile groups in the country is increasing year on year. In his dissertation on the economic and mathematical assessment of ways to increase the standard of living of the population of the Republic of Armenia [7], R. Ghazaryan evaluates the standard of living of the population of the Republic of Armenia and the ways of its growth. The primary indicators of living standards identified were GDP per capita, human development and the level of inequality within the country. The paper identifies the primary

factors contributing to the wage gap in Armenia and assesses the influence of various economic and social determinants on wage levels. The paper analyses the relationship between economic growth and human development in Armenia, and reveals the nature of this mutual connection through empirical methods. The employed methods allow for the investigation of the relationship between the level of inequality in Armenia and foreign direct investment, as well as the assessment of the impact of these and a number of other factors on the level of inequality through the utilization of empirical methods [8].

Methodology

During the study, an attempt was made to assess the role of various macroeconomic factors, including internal and external factors influencing changes in living standards, using a vector autoregressive model. In the first stage, the following 3 groups of indicators were selected. *Internal factors:* Consumer price index compared to the same month last year, Unemployment rate, The share of consumer loans in GDP, State budget revenues, Expenditures of the state budget, The share of household consumption in total consumer spending. *External factors:* The average monthly exchange rate of the US dollar, Personal money transfers to Armenia, the balance of the financial account in accordance with the balance of payments, million US dollars. Factors characterizing the standard of living: GDP per capita, The level of poverty, Gin coefficient, Average monthly nominal salary.

The study used quarterly data for the selected indicators for the years 2008-2024. For those indicators for which quarterly data were not available (Gini coefficient and poverty level), their annual series, converted to quarterly using the linear interpolation method, were used.

Table 1

Designations used in the model and their meaning.

Designation	Meaning
d_cpicomparedtosamemonth	CPI compared to the same month last year (differenced)
d_unemployment	Unemployment rate (differenced)
d_consumerloanstogdpdollar	Share of consumer loans in GDP (differenced)
d_expensesstatebudget	State budget revenues (differenced)
d_statebudgetrevenues	State budget expenditures (differenced)
fevd_d_householdconsumptionshar	Share of household consumption in total consumption (differenced)
d_exchangerate	Average monthly USD exchange rate (differenced)
d_moneytransfers	Personal money transfers to RA (differenced)
d_financialaccountbalance	financial account balance (differenced)

At the subsequent stage of the analysis, the stationarity of the series was evaluated, specifically through the application of the Dickie-Fuller and Phillips-Perron tests, which demonstrated that a subset of the series exhibited non-stationary characteristics. In order to ascertain whether the ranks were stationary, the differences between the ranks, as well as the discrepancies between each quarterly cost and its preceding one, were calculated. The subsequent step was to construct a vector autoregression (VAR) model utilising the statistical software application Stata. In order to ensure the correct

ordering of the factors within the VAR system, the endogeneity/exogeneity levels of the indicators were evaluated using the Granger causality test. The indicators included in the system, which are influenced by numerous factors and/or explain a smaller number of indicators, are relatively more endogenous; thus, they are placed at the end in the order of the VAR indicator table. The indicators that exert a greater influence on other indicators and are to a lesser extent influenced by them, that is, those that are relatively exogenous, were included at the outset of the process. As a result of the tests, the indicators were included in the model in a

clear order, from those that are relatively exogenous to those that are endogenous, from those that are less influenced by other indicators in the system to those that more strongly determine other indicators in the system:

1. Average monthly nominal salary
2. Gin Coefficient
3. GDP per capita
4. The share of household consumption in total consumer spending
5. Expenditures of the state budget
6. State budget revenues
7. The share of consumer loans in GDP
8. Unemployment rate
9. The level of poverty
10. Financial account balance

11. Personal money transfers to Armenia
12. The average monthly exchange rate of the US dollar
13. Consumer price index compared to the same month last year

The results of the test indicate that the internal and external factors selected in the system have a relatively minor impact on changes in the standard of living. Furthermore, the indicators characterizing the standard of living are primarily exogenous, exerting a greater influence on the selected internal and external factors than vice versa. The VAR was reconstructed in accordance with the specified order of indicators, ranging from exogenous to endogenous within the developed system. The resulting outcome is presented below.

Table 2.

VAR summary

Sample: 2009q3 - 2024q1	Number of obs	=	59
Log likelihood = -3149.536	AIC	=	120.5266
FPE = 4.52e+35	HQIC	=	126.1073
Det(Sigma_ml) = 1.30e+29	SBIC	=	134.8229

Equation	Parms	RMSE	R-sq	chi2	P>chi2
d_monthlyaverag~y	29	10356.7	0.6437	106.5866	0.0000
d_giniincagg	29	.002103	0.6283	99.65353	0.0000
d_gdppercapita	29	30.8174	0.7636	190.6235	0.0000
d_householdcon~e	29	2.96166	0.6093	92.02978	0.0000
d_expensesstat~t	29	522927	0.7426	170.2378	0.0000
d_statebudgetr~s	29	439176	0.7343	163.0607	0.0000
d_consumerloan~r	29	.302626	0.7312	160.5269	0.0000
d_unemployment	29	1.19086	0.7421	169.7825	0.0000
d_poverty	29	.299423	0.8306	289.3385	0.0000
d_studentenroll	29	.446888	0.7116	145.5731	0.0000
d_financialacc~e	29	143.448	0.7846	214.9532	0.0000
d_moneytransfers	29	87.9469	0.8299	287.7685	0.0000
d_exchangerate	29	9.1588	0.7378	166.0211	0.0000
d_cpicomparedt~h	29	1.4801	0.6624	115.7539	0.0000

Having checked whether the selected lag is the optimal one, it can be stated that, according to most criteria, the preferred lag for the model is the second.

Table 3.

Information criteria for choosing the optimal lag

Selection-order criteria								
Sample: 2009q3 - 2024q1								
lag	LL	LR	df	p	FPE	AIC	HQIC	SBIC
0	-3701.48				2.8e+37	125.948	126.141	126.441*
1	-3380.68	641.6	196	0.000	4.7e+35	121.718	124.604*	129.113
2	-3149.54	462.28*	196	0.000	4.5e+35*	120.527*	126.107	134.823

When choosing higher lags, the model does not satisfy the stability condition, which is fulfilled for the second lag.

Table 4.

Results of the stability (stationarity) test of the model
Eigenvalue stability condition

Eigenvalue	Modulus
-.01566573 + .9132698i	.913404
-.01566573 - .9132698i	.913404
.8477589	.847759
.8086671 + .1818223i	.828856
.8086671 - .1818223i	.828856
-.8213125	.821313
-.03853367 + .7927021i	.793638
-.03853367 - .7927021i	.793638
.6407414 + .4202478i	.766262
.6407414 - .4202478i	.766262
-.1094916 + .7455759i	.753573
-.1094916 - .7455759i	.753573
-.5895003 + .3382293i	.679639
-.5895003 - .3382293i	.679639
-.2910119 + .5853081i	.653662
-.2910119 - .5853081i	.653662
.4621341 + .4055992i	.614881
.4621341 - .4055992i	.614881
-.5110774 + .3378116i	.612631
-.5110774 - .3378116i	.612631
.2463385 + .4945919i	.552543
.2463385 - .4945919i	.552543
-.3038084 + .4339559i	.529733
-.3038084 - .4339559i	.529733
.4448725	.444873
-.1833738 + .09049429i	.204488
-.1833738 - .09049429i	.204488
.1079315	.107932

All the eigenvalues lie inside the unit circle.
VAR satisfies stability condition.

In order to consider the constructed VAR significant, it is necessary that the selected delayed model

does not have autocorrelation, which documents the test result shown in the figure.

Table 5.

Autocorrelation test results
Lagrange-multiplier test

lag	chi2	df	Prob > chi2
1	311.9951	196	0.00000
2	170.9149	196	0.90172

H0: no autocorrelation at lag order

Analysis and results:

Moreover, the responses of five indicators that characterise the standard of living to the shock from selected internal and external factors were revealed. The graph illustrates the impact of a positive shock in the amount of one standard deviation unit in the corresponding indicator line on GDP per capita over the subsequent 16 quarters. The results demonstrate that among the factors considered, the share of consumer loans in GDP, as well as relatively lower unemployment and inflation, have the most pronounced impact. In particular, an increase in the proportion of consumer loans relative to a standard deviation has a negative impact on GDP per capita over the following two years. The initial shock has a detrimental impact on income distribution, poverty levels, and average monthly wages. Conversely, it has a favourable impact on these

variables, although the positive effects are gradually diminishing. The aforementioned effects of consumer lending can be attributed to the nature of the cash flows generated by such lending. While this has a positive effect on consumption, subsequent negative flows generated by lending result in a reduction in the volume of further consumption. Furthermore, the periodic nature of economic development gives rise to additional risks for households in the context of this type of lending. A further decrease in income may create difficulties in repaying the loan. The issue may become more pronounced. Furthermore, inflation and its expectations can also precipitate shifts in the current reduction in consumption or its dynamics, thereby altering the behaviour of households. With regard to other indicators, including budget revenues and expenditures, GDP per

capita and indicators characterising the standard of living in general, the reactions are relatively insignificant.

With regard to the influence of state budgetary revenues and expenditures, it is evident that the impact of these on GDP per capita can be discerned by examining the reaction of the latter to the former's shocks. In the initial two quarters, the impact is observed to be negative; however, following this period, the impact is seen to become neutralized through the fading of fluctuations.

Taxation ultimately results in a reduction of income for both organizations and households, which in turn has a detrimental impact on the growth rate of GDP. This phenomenon can be attributed to two factors: firstly, the level of taxation exceeds the optimal tax burden, and secondly, the inefficiency of the state spending policy and its low level of inclusiveness.

The preponderance of current expenditures among public funds, while conducive to the growth of the population's income, fails to engender further impact on the increase in productivity, thereby nullifying its subsequent effects.

This is the reason why the impact of state budget expenditures on GDP per capita in the first three quarters was positive, after which the impact was reduced to zero again due to fading fluctuations. The influence of the state budget on other factors that contribute to the overall standard of living is comparatively limited. In particular, income policy generates a certain growth in the initial period, which can be explained by the initial negative impact of income policy on economic growth. However, in the future, this influence is positive, which we can further attribute to this shortcoming. It is possible that this can be attributed to unproductive and low inclusivity.

Graph 6. Responses of Per Capita GDP to One Standard Deviation Changes in Government Budget Revenues

Graph 7. Responses of Per Capita GDP to One Standard Deviation Changes in Government Budget Expenditures

Graph 8. Responses of the Share of Household Consumption in Total Consumption to One Standard Deviation Changes in Government Budget Revenues

Graph 9. Responses of the Share of Household Consumption in Total Consumption to One Standard Deviation Changes in Government Budget Expenditures

Graph 10. Responses of the Share of Household Consumption in Total Consumption to One Standard Deviation Changes in Government Budget Revenues

Graph 11. Responses of the Share of Household Consumption in Total Consumption to One Standard Deviation Changes in Government Budget Expenditures

Graph 12. Responses of the Poverty Rate to One Standard Deviation Changes in Government Budget Revenues

Graph 13. Responses of the Poverty Rate to One Standard Deviation Changes in Government Budget Expenditures

Graph 14. Responses of the Average Nominal Monthly Wage to One Standard Deviation Changes in Government Budget Revenues

Graph 15. Responses of the Average Nominal Monthly Wage to One Standard Deviation Changes in Government Budget Expenditures

Furthermore, the growth patterns of indicators describing the standard of living were addressed, with a particular focus on elucidating the extent to which changes in the factor under consideration can be attributed to internal and external indicators included in the system. The Cholesky decomposition was employed to yield the following results.

The Tables 6-10 in applications illustrates the proportion of the change in GDP per capita that can be attributed to each indicator for the corresponding quarter.

For the sake of brevity, only cases of internal and external factors have been presented. To illustrate, 4.29% of the change in GDP per capita in the second quarter can be attributed to the unemployment rate, which is the highest among the factors considered in this lag. Therefore, the collective effect of internal and external factors on the standard of living in the second quarter can be seen to account for approximately 10% of the observed change in GDP per capita. The changes in the

volume of household consumption in the second quarter are to a greater extent than individual internal and external factors, due to changes in the balance of the financial account, government budget expenditures and the exchange rate of the US dollar to the dram. The Gin coefficient is most susceptible to influence from money transfers. The greatest impact on the poverty level is exerted by unemployment, consumer loans and government budget expenditures. Income is influenced by a number of factors, including the balance of the financial account, consumer loans, state budget revenues and expenditures.

The order of importance of the role of observed internal and external factors in changes in indicators characterising the standard of living, in accordance with the decrease in the overall effect over a four-year period: The share of consumer loans in GDP, the balance of the financial account in accordance with the balance of payments, The average monthly exchange rate of the US dollar, Expenditures of the state budget, Unemployment rate, Personal money transfers to Armenia, State budget revenues, Consumer price index compared to the same month last year.

In consideration of the influence of state budget revenues and expenditures on fluctuations in indicators that reflect the standard of living over the projected four-year period, it is notable that the former exerts a considerable impact on changes in the average monthly wage nomenclature, with an average contribution of 5.5%, and the share of household consumption in total consumption, with an average contribution of 2.2%. The role of budgets in GDP per capita and wage changes is relatively higher, with an average contribution of 1.6% and 1.8%, respectively.

Conclusions:

Summarizing the results of the analysis, we can note that

- The share of consumer loans in GDP has the most significant impact within the framework of the factors considered, while a relatively smaller impact is observed with respect to unemployment and inflation.
- A significant reduction in income resulting from unemployment has a significant impact on consumption volumes.
- Additionally, inflation and its associated expectations can influence the current reduction in consumption or its dynamics, thereby modifying household behaviour.
- The impact of state budget revenues on GDP per capita in the initial two quarters was negative; however, this effect was subsequently neutralised by the attenuation of fluctuations.

- The impact of government budget expenditures on GDP per capita during the initial three quarters was positive, after which the effect was reduced to zero due to the influence of fading fluctuations.

- The influence of state budget revenues on changes in indicators that characterise the standard of living is significant, particularly in the case of average monthly nominal wages (on average 5.5%) and the share of household consumption in total consumption (on average 2.2%).

- State budget expenditures exert a relatively greater influence on changes in GDP per capita and wages, with an average impact of 1.6% and 1.8%, respectively.

- A study of the growth structure of individual indicators reveals that 4.29% of the change in GDP per capita in the second quarter will be associated with the unemployment rate, which is the most significant factor among those considered in this lag. Furthermore, the lowest percentage was observed in the case of money transfers (0%).

- Based on the observations and forecasts, it can be posited that the collective effect of internal and external factors on living standards in the second quarter accounts for approximately 10% of the observed change in GDP per capita.

- The observed changes in the volume of consumption of the population in the second quarter are of a considerable magnitude in comparison with a number of selected internal and external factors, including changes in the balance of the financial account, government budget expenditures and the exchange rate of the US dollar against the dram. The most significant impact on the Gin coefficient is exerted by remittances, while unemployment, consumer loans and government budget expenditures have the greatest impact on poverty. Income is influenced by a number of factors, including the balance of the financial account, consumer loans, state budget revenues and budget expenditures.

- The sequence of importance of roles in changes in indicators characterising the standard of living, depending on the decrease in the overall effect over four years, is as follows: the share of consumer loans in GDP, the balance of the financial account in accordance with the balance of payments, the average monthly exchange rate of the US dollar, state budget expenditures, unemployment rate, personal money transfers to Armenia, state budget revenues and CPI.

Applications.

Graphs by irfname, impulse variable, and response variable

Figure 1 Reaction of GDP per capita to changes in indicators per unit of standard deviation

Graphs by irfname, impulse variable, and response variable

Figure 2. The share of household expenditure on final consumption in total consumer spending

Figure 3. The reation of the Ginii coefficient to changes in indicators per unit of standard deviation

Figure 4. The reaction of the poverty level to changes in indicators per unit of standard deviation

Figure 5. The reaction of the average monthly nominal salary to changes in indicators per unit of standard deviation

Table 6.

Shares of factors explaining changes in GDP per capita

Lag	State budget expenditures	State budget revenues	Share of Consumer Loans in GDP	Unemployment rate	Financial Account Balance	Personal Monetary Transfers to Armenia	Average Monthly USD Exchange Rate	CPI - Consumer Price Index	Total
1	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
2	1.49%	1.59%	0.04%	4.29%	0.98%	0.00%	1.63%	0.02%	10.02%
3	1.11%	1.66%	3.46%	5.48%	1.73%	0.03%	1.22%	0.07%	14.77%
4	1.47%	1.66%	3.79%	5.15%	1.66%	0.06%	1.32%	0.45%	15.56%
5	1.84%	1.64%	4.40%	4.70%	2.38%	0.06%	1.28%	0.71%	17.02%
6	1.73%	1.55%	4.62%	4.44%	2.25%	0.22%	1.21%	0.77%	16.79%
7	1.67%	1.65%	5.46%	4.29%	2.22%	0.60%	1.15%	0.82%	17.86%
8	1.79%	1.68%	5.94%	4.29%	2.34%	0.59%	1.17%	0.81%	18.60%
9	1.79%	1.69%	5.94%	4.24%	2.69%	0.58%	1.20%	0.82%	18.95%
10	1.77%	1.68%	6.05%	4.19%	2.76%	0.61%	1.18%	0.82%	19.07%
11	1.76%	1.69%	6.17%	4.17%	2.75%	0.71%	1.18%	0.81%	19.24%
12	1.81%	1.72%	6.24%	4.22%	2.77%	0.71%	1.17%	0.81%	19.44%
13	1.80%	1.72%	6.21%	4.21%	2.82%	0.71%	1.24%	0.80%	19.52%
14	1.81%	1.72%	6.19%	4.20%	2.82%	0.71%	1.25%	0.80%	19.50%
15	1.81%	1.72%	6.19%	4.20%	2.83%	0.72%	1.25%	0.81%	19.51%
16	1.81%	1.72%	6.18%	4.21%	2.83%	0.73%	1.25%	0.81%	19.54%
Average	1.59%	1.57%	4.80%	4.14%	2.24%	0.44%	1.17%	0.63%	16.59%

Shares of factors explaining the change in the share of household consumption in total consumption

Lag	State budget expenditures	State budget revenues	Share of Consumer Loans in GDP	Unemployment rate	Financial Account Balance	Personal Monetary Transfers to Armenia	Average Monthly USD Exchange Rate	CPI - Consumer Price Index	Total
1	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
2	1.62%	0.05%	0.28%	0.03%	4.00%	0.84%	1.45%	0.34%	8.60%
3	1.56%	0.10%	1.69%	0.76%	5.67%	2.62%	2.84%	0.31%	15.55%
4	1.56%	0.22%	1.81%	2.32%	5.48%	3.44%	4.02%	0.29%	19.13%
5	1.57%	0.22%	1.63%	2.40%	5.31%	3.15%	4.84%	0.36%	19.48%
6	2.47%	0.23%	1.49%	2.40%	5.25%	2.88%	4.90%	0.41%	20.04%
7	2.58%	0.23%	1.55%	2.43%	5.44%	2.90%	4.89%	0.41%	20.43%
8	2.64%	0.24%	1.53%	2.61%	5.44%	2.98%	4.85%	0.42%	20.72%
9	2.61%	0.24%	1.53%	2.87%	5.41%	2.96%	4.91%	0.42%	20.96%
10	2.64%	0.23%	1.50%	2.82%	5.47%	2.91%	4.99%	0.44%	21.01%
11	2.65%	0.24%	1.51%	2.84%	5.57%	2.91%	5.00%	0.44%	21.14%
12	2.64%	0.24%	1.50%	2.85%	5.58%	2.93%	4.99%	0.44%	21.17%
13	2.64%	0.24%	1.50%	2.89%	5.59%	2.94%	4.99%	0.44%	21.23%
14	2.64%	0.24%	1.50%	2.88%	5.60%	2.93%	5.00%	0.44%	21.23%
15	2.64%	0.24%	1.50%	2.89%	5.63%	2.93%	5.01%	0.44%	21.27%
16	2.63%	0.24%	1.50%	2.89%	5.63%	2.93%	5.00%	0.44%	21.27%
Average	2.19%	0.20%	1.38%	2.24%	5.07%	2.64%	4.23%	0.38%	18.33%

Contribution of Factors to Changes in the Gini Coefficient

Lag	State budget expenditures	State budget revenues	Share of Consumer Loans in GDP	Unemployment rate	Financial Account Balance	Personal Monetary Transfers to Armenia	Average Monthly USD Exchange Rate	CPI - Consumer Price Index	Total
1	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
2	0.00%	0.00%	0.24%	0.00%	0.35%	0.52%	0.28%	0.21%	1.60%
3	0.12%	0.04%	0.80%	0.54%	1.05%	1.21%	1.70%	0.20%	5.65%
4	0.12%	0.04%	1.22%	0.67%	1.21%	1.62%	2.09%	0.26%	7.23%
5	0.28%	0.04%	1.84%	0.65%	1.42%	1.79%	2.13%	0.30%	8.46%
6	0.32%	0.05%	2.11%	0.65%	1.51%	1.80%	2.14%	0.31%	8.90%
7	0.32%	0.06%	2.28%	0.66%	1.57%	1.80%	2.14%	0.34%	9.18%
8	0.36%	0.09%	2.38%	0.66%	1.57%	1.80%	2.16%	0.34%	9.36%
9	0.38%	0.12%	2.40%	0.66%	1.57%	1.79%	2.21%	0.34%	9.46%
10	0.38%	0.13%	2.39%	0.67%	1.57%	1.79%	2.22%	0.34%	9.50%
11	0.38%	0.14%	2.39%	0.67%	1.58%	1.79%	2.23%	0.34%	9.51%
12	0.38%	0.14%	2.39%	0.67%	1.57%	1.78%	2.23%	0.34%	9.51%
13	0.38%	0.14%	2.39%	0.67%	1.57%	1.78%	2.24%	0.34%	9.52%
14	0.38%	0.14%	2.39%	0.67%	1.57%	1.78%	2.24%	0.34%	9.52%
15	0.38%	0.14%	2.39%	0.67%	1.57%	1.78%	2.24%	0.35%	9.53%
16	0.38%	0.14%	2.40%	0.67%	1.58%	1.78%	2.24%	0.35%	9.53%
Average	0.29%	0.09%	1.88%	0.57%	1.33%	1.55%	1.90%	0.29%	7.90%

Contribution of Factors to Changes in the Poverty Rate

Lag	State budget expenditures	State budget revenues	Share of Consumer Loans in GDP	Unemployment rate	Financial Account Balance	Personal Monetary Transfers to Armenia	Average Monthly USD Exchange Rate	CPI - Consumer Price Index	Total
1	3.18%	0.41%	5.04%	1.87%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	10.51%
2	1.84%	0.34%	3.31%	4.17%	0.65%	0.19%	0.62%	0.00%	11.12%
3	1.45%	0.52%	2.87%	3.15%	0.77%	0.44%	3.22%	0.09%	12.51%
4	1.32%	0.47%	3.66%	2.71%	1.60%	1.14%	4.09%	0.17%	15.17%
5	1.51%	0.43%	4.71%	2.47%	2.17%	1.27%	4.34%	0.22%	17.12%
6	1.50%	0.42%	5.23%	2.37%	2.58%	1.39%	4.22%	0.28%	18.00%
7	1.47%	0.44%	5.66%	2.32%	2.90%	1.52%	4.15%	0.31%	18.78%
8	1.47%	0.51%	6.03%	2.29%	2.98%	1.60%	4.10%	0.33%	19.31%
9	1.53%	0.57%	6.22%	2.30%	3.02%	1.58%	4.08%	0.33%	19.64%
10	1.52%	0.60%	6.20%	2.30%	3.11%	1.57%	4.11%	0.33%	19.75%
11	1.52%	0.62%	6.18%	2.29%	3.13%	1.57%	4.10%	0.33%	19.73%
12	1.51%	0.63%	6.18%	2.29%	3.13%	1.57%	4.09%	0.33%	19.73%
13	1.52%	0.63%	6.17%	2.30%	3.12%	1.57%	4.10%	0.33%	19.74%
14	1.51%	0.63%	6.17%	2.30%	3.12%	1.57%	4.10%	0.33%	19.75%
15	1.52%	0.63%	6.17%	2.29%	3.12%	1.57%	4.10%	0.34%	19.75%
16	1.52%	0.63%	6.17%	2.29%	3.13%	1.57%	4.10%	0.34%	19.75%
Average	1.62%	0.53%	5.37%	2.48%	2.41%	1.26%	3.59%	0.25%	17.52%

Table 10.

Contribution of Factors to Changes in the Average Nominal Monthly Wage

Lag	State budget expenditures	State budget revenues	Share of Consumer Loans in GDP	Unemployment rate	Financial Account Balance	Personal Monetary Transfers to Armenia	Average Monthly USD Exchange Rate	CPI - Consumer Price Index	Total
1	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
2	0.99%	1.24%	2.03%	0.00%	3.78%	0.47%	0.35%	0.01%	8.88%
3	2.31%	1.80%	3.31%	0.02%	3.58%	1.05%	0.38%	0.11%	12.56%
4	2.86%	1.68%	3.35%	0.02%	3.89%	1.72%	0.38%	0.14%	14.05%
5	6.18%	1.96%	3.44%	0.05%	3.54%	1.99%	0.76%	0.16%	18.09%
6	6.42%	2.08%	3.92%	0.21%	3.58%	1.93%	1.26%	0.18%	19.59%
7	6.79%	2.04%	3.87%	0.21%	3.58%	1.91%	1.27%	0.20%	19.87%
8	6.77%	2.01%	4.11%	0.36%	3.84%	1.90%	1.27%	0.20%	20.47%
9	6.88%	1.99%	4.09%	0.48%	3.92%	1.92%	1.27%	0.20%	20.74%
10	6.86%	1.98%	4.15%	0.47%	4.29%	1.92%	1.37%	0.20%	21.24%
11	6.98%	2.00%	4.15%	0.47%	4.28%	1.92%	1.39%	0.20%	21.40%
12	6.95%	1.99%	4.20%	0.51%	4.44%	1.95%	1.39%	0.20%	21.64%
13	7.01%	1.99%	4.19%	0.53%	4.42%	1.99%	1.39%	0.20%	21.72%
14	7.00%	1.98%	4.25%	0.53%	4.55%	1.99%	1.42%	0.20%	21.92%
15	7.03%	1.99%	4.25%	0.54%	4.55%	1.99%	1.42%	0.20%	21.97%
16	7.02%	1.98%	4.27%	0.55%	4.63%	2.01%	1.42%	0.20%	22.08%
Average	5.50%	1.80%	3.60%	0.31%	3.80%	1.67%	1.05%	0.16%	17.89%

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